

MODEL BORDER TRADE COLLABORATION OF THAI-LAO CONSUMER GOODS ENTREPRENEURS NONG KHAI BORDER CHECKPOINT, THAILAND

Praphat Surachawala*

Ph.D. Student in Development Strategy
Udon Thani Rajabhat University, Thailand

Krittikar Sanposh

Associate Professor, Faculty of Development Strategy
Udon Thani Rajabhat University, Thailand

Bussagorn Suksan

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Development Strategy
Udon Thani Rajabhat University, Thailand

*Corresponding Author

ABSTRACT

The objectives of this article were to 1) To study the problems of border trade cooperation Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border crossing, Thailand and 2) Design a model for cross-border trade cooperation Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border crossing, Thailand. This research is developmental and divided into 2 phases: Mixed qualitative and quantitative research. Phase 1 studies the problem the problems of border trade cooperation Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border crossing, Thailand, Uses research The target group was 15 experts, and the sample group was determined to be 384 people, research tools include semi-structured interviews and questionnaires, analyzing the content data and using statistics, frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation, phase 2 Design a model for cross-border trade cooperation Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border crossing, Thailand. used by organizing a workshop. Target groups include 15 experts and 30 experts, confirming the model suitability and feasibility.

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The research tools were suitability and feasibility assessment forms. To analyze data using statistics, frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. Research results. The problems of border trade cooperation Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border crossing, Thailand. found that ranked 1 information and communication technology exchange, 2 trust building, 3 negotiation, 4 setting common goals, 5 reaching an agreement, 6 joint decision-making, 7 evaluation, 8 building harmony, 9 joint database management, and 10 planning, respectively and the model design for cross-border trade cooperation among Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border crossing, Thailand, revealed that the highest priority was the exchange of information and communication technology, with 5 development activities; the second was trust-building, with 9 development activities; the third was negotiation, with 7 development activities; and the fourth was joint goal-setting, with 8 development activities. The evaluation of the model's suitability and feasibility indicated that both overall value higher than 3.51 which is considered acceptable based on the assessment criteria that have been established.

Keywords: Model, Cooperation, Cross-Border Trade, Consumer Goods Entrepreneur

Cite this Article: Praphat Surachawala, Krittikar Sanposh, Bussagorn Suksan, Model Border Trade Collaboration of Thai-Lao Consumer Goods Entrepreneurs Nong Khai Border Checkpoint, Thailand. *International Journal of Management*, 15(6), 120–130.
https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJM/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_6/IJM_15_06_010.pdf

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2015, Thailand launched the ASEAN Economic Community under the vision of “Creating an ASEAN Economic Community with high competitiveness, clear rules, and people-centeredness.” The community will help the overall economy of the region expand by 7.1 percent compared to the case without the community and will create 14 million more jobs by 2025. For this reason, trade in the Northeastern region is a very important region for Thailand regarding border trade because it is a region with high potential suitable for development and linkage with neighboring countries, especially Lao PDR. In the past, there have been various forms of joint economic activities that are becoming opportunities to develop it into a new production base for the industrial sector, which will benefit economic development at the regional and national levels extensively. (National Economic and Social Development Council , 2018)

The Thai-Laos border in the northeastern part of Thailand is mostly the Mekong River. In some places, you can see communities of various sizes stretching along the banks of the Mekong River, such as in Khemmarat District, Thailand. On the opposite side of Khemmarat District is Ban Tha Pat Chum in Laos. Near Ban Tha Pat Chum, there are more than 10 villages along the banks of the Mekong River. Or further from the riverbank in Khemmarat District, Thailand, which is the location of the trade relaxation point, you will see people traveling across the border by motorboats. If you observe carefully, you will find that there are various consumer goods exported from Thailand to Laos. And if you follow the export of goods loaded by motorboats to the opposite side, you will find that some of the goods will be distributed to shops in various villages near Ban Tha Pat Chum in Laos. While a large amount of goods will be loaded on small or medium-sized trucks to be transported to inner cities (districts) that may be as much as 100 kilometers deep to be delivered to large wholesalers before the goods are sold to neighboring cities or villages. Border trade between Thailand and Lao PDR: Thailand has a border trade surplus and it has been increasing all the time. Border trade between Thailand and Lao PDR has the third highest trade value after Malaysia and Myanmar. In the past 5 years, the trade value increased by an average of approximately 17.3 percent per year. In 2012, the trade value was approximately 132,000 million baht. During that period, Thailand had a trade surplus that increased by an average of approximately 22.2 percent per year.

In 2012, Thailand had a border trade surplus of approximately 86,000 million baht. Diesel is the export product with the highest value, followed by cars, computer equipment and components, gasoline, construction machinery and components. For important imported goods, copper and products are the highest value imported goods, accounting for approximately 70 percent of the total import value in 2012, followed by processed wood, vegetables and vegetable preparations. The main cross-border trade channels are the permanent border checkpoints of Nong Khai and Mukdahan, and statistical data on imports and exports of border trade between Thailand and the Lao PDR in 2022. In imports worth 260,702 Million baht export 350,627 million baht and trade balance with Lao PDR 350,627 One million baht (Department of Foreign Trade, (2023) because the import and export rates of goods have been increasing continuously and it is a country that is connected to the export of goods related to the next countries such as China and Vietnam (Kantphan Techadechaphiphat , Wichithra Srison and Santhan Chayanon, 2022)

Thailand is the country with the second largest investment in Laos after China, with a total of 752 projects worth a total of 4,492 million US dollars. Most of the investment is in trade, services, handicrafts, hotels, restaurants, processed agricultural products, and energy businesses. These are all opportunities for Thai entrepreneurs. Therefore, there are still many opportunities for Thai products in Laos to grow because Laos does not have its own domestic manufacturing plants. Most consumer products are imported from abroad, and Thai products and services are well-known, familiar, and accepted in Laos. In addition, the value of trade between Thailand and Laos has been increasing steadily. In addition, Laos has also received interest from foreign investors, including China, Japan, South Korea, and France. Therefore, we cannot just look at the population size of the country because there are also foreigners who travel to invest and travel in Laos. It is also a transit point to southern China and Vietnam. The import-export process is still complicated and inconvenient for doing business because importing goods from Laos must be done through a government agency called Lao Import-Export (Society Lao Import-Export). Obstacles that may affect the development of Thailand's trade potential are found to include both physical structural problems and problems in facilitating transportation routes, such as transportation routes in Laos with rather winding roads and insufficient facilities. There is also uncertainty in the fee rates and private companies that are permitted by the Ministry of Commerce to import-export goods according to the types or categories permitted by the government only. The international trade system of Laos is not yet international and policies and regulations are frequently changed. Transportation in Laos is also inconvenient because land transportation of goods in Laos mainly uses cars, which are still rugged and the transportation of goods still relies more on human labor than machines, which makes transportation time long and goods easily damaged. Another problem of border trade is the unequal development of the two countries, which makes it impossible to connect smoothly. It can be concluded that the main source of obstacles to border trade between Thailand and Laos is the failure of public administration on both sides of Thailand and Laos. In facilitating trade between the two countries (Kamonthip Tridech, 2018)

From the above situation, it can be seen that the export value and trade balance tend to increase every year. However, the Thai-Laos border trade also has a problematic situation that must be resolved. From the research report on the border trade problem, it was found that the transportation problem has high costs, lack of labor, and the infrastructure is not conducive to trade. The opportunity is that Laos is the center of Thai products to Vietnam and China. The obstacle is that there is a lack of professional proactive marketers and counterfeit products. As for the development guidelines for the Thai-Laos border trade economy in the upper northeastern region, Laos is a country with abundant natural resources, suitable for investment. There are physical conditions and problems, economics and society in the border area of Thailand-Laos People's Democratic Republic in Loei Province. It has a high potential for development, but still lacks opportunities in terms of support and investment. It is a connection point with other regions both inside and outside the country. Government measures and the work of officials and strategies for border trade and investment promotion have an influence on investment decisions. Border trade entrepreneurs have knowledge and understanding of government policies and projects, such as promoting and developing Thai-Laos border trade to be able to develop border trade operations appropriately.

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In conducting border trade businesses, the development guidelines for the Thai-Laos border trade economy should be implemented. (Kulpat Kamol , Banphot Wirunrat and Suchanee Methiyothin, 2020)

For the above reasons, the researcher sees the importance of studying the border trade cooperation model of Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand, in order to use the obtained data as a cooperation model to promote, support and solve problems that occur with Thai-Lao border trade businesses in order to create business strength and competitive advantages that are accepted and sustainably exist in the ASEAN and global levels.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THIS STUDY

- 1.To study the problems of border trade cooperation between Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand.
- 2.To Design a model for cross-border trade cooperation Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border crossing, Thailand

III. DELIMITATION OF THIS STUDY

The key informants are experts and senior executives, civil servants, local administrators, and consumer goods entrepreneurs from Thailand to Laos at the Nong Khai border checkpoint. The selection criteria are persons with at least 5 years of experience. Data collection method for qualitative research of 15 people. The research instrument used a structured interview. How to collect data in quantitative research and the sample group was determined to be 348 people and distributed questionnaires.

IV. METHOD IN THIS STUDY

It is a mixed research method using both qualitative and quantitative research methods carried out in 2 phases as follows:

Phase 1 research studies the problems of border trade cooperation between Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand.It was a variety of research. There are 2 steps as follows:

Step 1 study the the problems of border trade cooperation between Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand. Qualitative research The target group is 15 experts senior executives, civil servants, local administrators, and Thai-Laos consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border checkpoint. Selection criteria. By selecting a specific type the research instrument used was a semi-structured interview. Data collection was done with Data analysis using content analysis and summary analysis.

Step 2 study the the problems of border trade cooperation between Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand.conducting Quantitative Method Research The population is Thai-Laos consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border checkpoint. The sample group: Since the exact population is unknown, the sample size can be calculated from the formula in the case of an unknown population of WGCochran by setting a confidence level, Sample group used Yamane formula with a confidence level of 95 percent and an error of 5 percent resulted in a sample of 384 people (Yamane, 1973) using a simple random sampling method were obtained. The tool used in the research was a questionnaire. 2 episodes as follows: Part 1: General information of the respondents.

Part 2 : Questionnaire to study the 2 study the the problems of border trade cooperation between Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand, Research tools: the researcher used a questionnaire created by the researcher himself by using data from literature studies that document concepts and theories; It is a 5-level estimation, divided into 3 parts, part 1 asks for basic information about the respondents. It is a checklist by asking about gender, age, education level, part 2 asked about the problem of organizing dual vocational education system. Bachelor's degree Northeastern Vocational Education Institute 1. It is a 5-level rating scale according to the Likert Method (Boonchom Srisaard, 2010)

Statistics based on data analysis are the percentage, mean, and standard deviation in the discussion of results; to describe the results obtained from a scale questionnaire. Estimated values considering the average score level according to 5 criteria (Boonchom Srisaat, 2010). The revised tool was then brought to the experts to check content validity and the language used and finally, scores from all 5 experts were taken to find the correspondence index between the items of each question with the purpose to be measured (Index of Item – Objective Congruence: IOC). This was achieved by using the formula of Rovinelli and Hambleton referred to in Boonchom Srisaat, (2010). The questionnaire's IOC value was 0.80-1.00. The questions were considered consistent with the content. The modified tool was later tested with a sample of 30 people to find the alpha coefficient (Alpha-coefficient) of the whole questionnaire using Cronbach's method (1970) (Cronbach), a value was 0.980. The method of data collection - The researcher distributed questionnaires, collected the data, and verified the completeness of the data in the questionnaire manually along with the questionnaire to interpret the results is the code according to the manual by entering the prepared code, saving, and processing. The data analysis obtained from closed-ended questionnaires and used as statistics mean analysis which was applied from Boonchom Srisaard (2010) as follows 5 level. Statistics based on data analysis are the percentage (Percentage), mean (Mean), and Standard Deviation (Standard Division: S.D.) in the discussion of results; (Class Interval) to describe the results obtained from a scale questionnaire. Estimated values considering the average score level according to 5 criteria (Boonchom Srisat, 2010).

Phase 2: To Design a Model Border Trade Collaboration of Thai-Lao Consumer Goods Entrepreneurs Nong Khai Border Checkpoint, Thailand

The research is divided into 2 steps as follows:

Step 1: Draft a model for cooperation in border trade between Thai-Laos consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border checkpoint in Thailand, as follows: The researcher used the results of the Phase 1 study as a framework for analyzing the internal and external environments using the SWOT technique to identify strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and obstacles through a workshop and consultation with the dissertation advisor. The target group is 15 qualified persons with knowledge and experience in border trade cooperation between Thai-Laos consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand. The selection criteria are as follows: 1) 4 executives of relevant agencies. 2) 4 academics and 3) Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs. Select Specific Analyze data using content analysis and summarize the overall.

Step 2: Evaluate the border trade cooperation model of Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand. Target group consisting of experts with knowledge and experience of not less than 5 years, with selection criteria divided into 2 groups: 1) a group of experts in development strategy, 5 people, and 2) a group of experts with knowledge and experience in developing border trade cooperation models for Thai-Laos consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand, 20 people, for a total of 30 people. By selecting a specific type Research tools It is an assessment of suitability and feasibility.

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The scoring criteria are in the form of a rating scale using the Liker Method (Yutt Kaewwan , 2002) . which has criteria for interpreting the average value, adapted from Boonchum Srisat (2011)

Data Collection 1) The researcher coordinated with the sample group to inform the objectives and benefits of the research and requested permission to collect data; 2) The researcher collected the data by calling the appointment in advance and then taking the assessment together with a request for cooperation; and 3) The researcher traveled to collect data by himself. Data analysis by content analysis and synthesis content then a descriptive overview was summarized and data analysis the researcher analyzed the data by using a ready-made program that analyzed frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The results were interpreted according to the following analytical criteria (Boonchom Srisaat, 2011).

Level 5 with a mean value between 4.51-5.00 suitability and feasibility is at the highest level.

Level 4 with a mean value between 3.51-4.50 suitability and feasibility is at a high level.

Level 3 with a mean value between 2.51-3.50 suitability and feasibility is at a moderate level.

Level 2 with a mean value between 1.51-2.50 suitability and feasibility is at a low level.

Level 1 with a mean value between 1.00-1.50 suitability and feasibility is at the lowest level.

The researcher has set the criteria, the assessment must have a means of no less than 3.51 to be considered the evaluation is passed criteria.

V. CONCLUSION

From the research on model for cooperation in border trade between Thai-Laos consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border checkpoint in Thailand, The results of the research were summarized as follows:

Phase 1 The results the study of the problems of border trade cooperation between Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand.

1. The qualitative research results by interviewing 15 people. Found that 1) Most of them are female, accounting for 53.33 percent, aged between 45–54 years, accounting for 53. 33 percent, master's degree level, accounting for, 80.00 percent and marital status, accounting for 60 percent, 2) Results of interviews with experts and opinions regarding problems in Thai-Laos consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border checkpoint in Thailand. Found that Problems, the highest-ranked was the exchange of information and communication technology, followed by trust-building, negotiation, joint goal-setting, agreement-making, joint decision-making, evaluation, reconciliation, shared database management, and planning, in that order.

2. The quantitative results, there were 384 people responding to the questionnaire and it was found that the majority were male, 314 people, or 81.77 percent; aged 55 years or older, 231 people, or 60.16 percent; had a bachelor's degree, 231 people, or 60.16 percent; and were married, 225 people, or 58.59 percent.. The results of the analysis of the model design for cross-border trade cooperation among Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border crossing, Thailand, revealed that the highest priority was the exchange of information and communication technology, with 5 development activities; the second was trust-building, with 9 development activities; the third was negotiation, with 7 development activities; and the fourth was joint goal-setting, with 8 development activities. The evaluation of the model's suitability and feasibility indicated that both were at a high level across all aspects were shown in Table

Table 1 The mean and standard deviation of the overall level of border trade cooperation problems of Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand.

Issues of cooperation	Problem level			number
	\bar{X}	S.D	level	
1. Information and communication technology exchange	3.408	0.492	moderate	1
2. Trust building	3.393	0.488	moderate	2
3. Negotiation	3.391	0.462	moderate	3
4. Joint goal setting	3.340	0.464	moderate	4
5. Agreement finding	3.302	0.489	moderate	5
6. Joint decision making	3.295	0.464	moderate	6
7. Evaluation	3.252	0.467	moderate	7
8. Solidarity building	3.240	0.521	moderate	8
9. Joint database management	3.239	0.479	moderate	9
10. Planning	3.217	0.483	moderate	10
together	4.340	0.693	moderate	

Phase 2 To Design a Model Border Trade Collaboration of Thai-Lao Consumer Goods Entrepreneurs Nong Khai Border Checkpoint, Thailand. Consists of Issues of cooperation including were as follows: 1st place in the area of information and communication technology exchange, with 5 development activities; 2nd place in the area of trust building, with 9 development activities; 3rd place in negotiation, with 7 development activities; and 4th place in setting common goals, with 8 development activities. The results of the evaluation of the appropriateness and feasibility of the model show that the overall appropriateness and feasibility are at a high level in all aspects. shown as Figure 1.

Figure 1 A Model Border Trade Collaboration of Thai-Lao Consumer Goods Entrepreneurs Nong Khai Border Checkpoint, Thailand.

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The researcher selected the level of the problem of border trade cooperation of Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand, which had an average value higher than the average value, in 4 areas as follows:

1st place: Information and communication technology exchange

2nd place: Trust building

3rd place: Negotiation

4th place: Joint goal setting

The researcher then used the results of the study in phase 1 as information for determining the development model of border trade cooperation of Thai-Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand, in phase 2.

Table 2 the evaluation of the appropriateness and feasibility a Model Border Trade Collaboration of Thai-Lao Consumer Goods Entrepreneurs Nong Khai Border Checkpoint, Thailand.

Model of consumer goods entrepreneurs	Appropriateness level			Possibility level		
	\bar{x}	S.D.	level	\bar{x}	S.D.	level
1. Information and communication technology exchange	4.34	0.59	high	4.41	0.63	high
2. Trust building	4.08	0.66	high	3.91	0.62	high
3. Negotiation	3.92	0.74	high	3.85	0.61	high
4. Joint goal setting	4.45	0.69	high	4.39	0.67	high
together	4.20	0.67	high	4.14	0.63	high

From Table 2 the evaluation of the appropriateness and feasibility a Model Border Trade Collaboration of Thai-Lao Consumer Goods Entrepreneurs Nong Khai Border Checkpoint, Thailand. It was found that the overall appropriateness was at a high level. while the feasibility of the strategy was at a high level. When considering each issue, it was at a high level in all aspects.

VI. DISCUSSION

The researcher brought the findings for discussion were as follows:

1. Results of the study on the problems of border trade cooperation between Thai -Lao consumer goods entrepreneurs at the Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand the top 4 were:

Rank 1 The exchange of information and communication technology was not fully communicated in the planning process. Data and plans were sent via email without meetings or follow-ups, leading to misunderstandings about schedules and operational goals. This is consistent with the research of Kulpat Kamol , Banphot Wirunrat, and Suchanee Methiyothin (2020) on the economic impact of border trade in the Northeast after the emergence of a new city in Vientiane, Lao People's Democratic Republic. The results of the study found that personnel development should be emphasized, developing people and society to be ready for changes in technology at all times.

Rank 2 In terms of building trust, past business history: Thai entrepreneurs have had problems with previous business partners regarding late delivery and non-compliance with contract terms, which created uncertainty for Lao entrepreneurs. Consistent with the research of Kantphan Techadechaphiphat , Wichithra Srison and Santhan Chayanon (2022) who conducted research on the strategy for cooperation in border trade between Thailand and the Lao People's Democratic Republic. The results of the study found that the development of traditional and cultural relations between the two countries should help strengthen the potential for Thai-Laos trade cooperation more reliably.

Rank 3 Negotiation: There is an imbalance in negotiating power. For example, Thailand is a specialized machinery manufacturer with a large market share and thus has more negotiating power. Meanwhile, Laos, an importer, has a high demand for the product but lacks other options. This imbalance makes them feel that they are not getting a fair offer and feel pressured to accept unsatisfactory terms. This is consistent with the research of Sudarat Sriubon and Chakrapan Khatchumsaeng (2019) who studied the cross-border economic role of small-scale Lao traders under development in the Greater Mekong Sub-region. The study found that the state's gaps in the management of unified border areas, coupled with the fact that small-scale Lao traders have various forms of capital, allow small-scale Lao traders to negotiate and change their roles to become actors.

Rank 4 Common Goal Setting, Different Business Visions Thai entrepreneurs focus on expanding regional markets to increase sales volume and reach new consumers, while Lao entrepreneurs It is necessary to focus on creating brand value and strengthening relationships with customers in the original market. This difference prevents both parties from setting consistent goals. This is consistent with the research of Maneerat Choticharee, Busakorn Sukhsaen, and Thanakrit Thurisut (2020) who researched the border trade cooperation model of Thai - Lao agricultural entrepreneurs, Bueng Kan Province, Thailand and Bolikhamxay Province, Lao People's Democratic Republic. The study found that entrepreneurs, government agencies, private sectors and business sectors must agree on the same direction and the same goal.

2. Results of the development model of border trade cooperation between Thai-Laos consumer goods entrepreneurs at Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand There are 4 sides in total: 2.1 Information and Communication Technology Exchange. Plans and activities include, 1) organizing seminars on new technologies related to border trade, such as the use of ERP systems, Big Data analysis, cloud Computing, and Digital Marketing, 2) training workshops on the use of software and information technology tools, such as Warehouse Management System, E-commerce system, and Customer Relationship Management System (CRM), 2.2. building Trust Plans and Activities include, 1) organizing seminars on the importance of trust and transparency in border trade, 2) organizing workshops on developing effective communication and negotiation skills to build trust among entrepreneurs; 2.3. negotiation has plans and activities including, 1) organize a workshop that focuses on developing negotiation skills and negotiation in various situations that occur in border areas, 2) Negotiation training through case studies and simulations that are close to real situations so that entrepreneurs can apply them in their businesses, 2.4. setting common goals Plans and activities include, 1) organizing workshops to enable entrepreneurs from bordering countries to jointly set consistent business goals, 2) training activities to create common goals through simulation activities related to border trade; and the development model of border trade cooperation between Thai-Laos consumer goods entrepreneurs, Nong Khai border checkpoint, Thailand The overall suitability and feasibility are at a high level. Consistent with the research of Manirat Choticharee, Busagorn Suksaen, and Thanakrit Thurisut (2020) who researched the border trade cooperation model of Thai - Lao agricultural entrepreneurs, Bueng Kan Province, Thailand and Bolikhamxay Province, Lao People's Democratic Republic. The study results found that the assessment of the Thai-Laos cross-border agricultural product transport manual by disseminating it to Thai-Laos agricultural product entrepreneurs must have an assessment result of suitability and feasibility higher than 3.51 to be considered to pass the assessment criteria that can be used as a guideline for actual practice.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the current study, the author recommends the following measures, as presented below:

1. Recommendations from the application of the research results. The research results should be applied as follows: 1.1 establishing an effective communication mechanism. Clear and consistent communication channels should be established between entrepreneurs from both countries, 1.2 promoting understanding of cultures and regulations, as entrepreneurs from both countries have differences in culture and trade regulations, 1.3 creating clear common goals. Entrepreneurs from both sides set clear and consistent goals for border trade operations.

1.4 using information technology to support operations. Data management and product tracking technologies are used in border trade to increase coordination efficiency and reduce errors. 1.5 solving negotiation and risk management issues. Creating a negotiation mechanism that emphasizes flexibility and transparency. 1.6 creating a long-term development plan. Creating sustainable cooperation should include a long-term development plan.

The research results of Phase 2 should be applied as follows:

1. Exchange of information and communication technology Recommendations Establish a central communication platform for entrepreneurs from both countries to exchange market information.

2. Building trust Recommendations Organize activities to build networks of entrepreneurs and civil society organizations in border areas.

3. Negotiation Recommendations Establish a border business negotiation center that provides legal, tax, and international agreement advice. Negotiation skills training for entrepreneurs

4. Joint goal setting Recommendations: Create a long-term border trade strategy plan with clear goals, such as increasing the volume of trade between the two countries or developing supporting infrastructure. Create a platform for cooperation between entrepreneurs and government officials from both sides to discuss common goals. Responsible agencies: Ministry of Commerce (Thailand), Ministry of Industry and Trade (Laos), International organizations, such as the United Nations Development Agency (UNDP). Benefits:

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Citation: Praphat Surachawala, Krittikar Sanposh, Bussagorn Suksan, Model Border Trade Collaboration of Thai-Lao Consumer Goods Entrepreneurs Nong Khai Border Checkpoint, Thailand. International Journal of Management, 15(6), 120–130.

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